

Mothering an Adolescent at Zunheboto Sadar: A Case Study

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Abstract:- Adolescence is known for its peculiar transitional stage which incorporation adolescents encountering different changes and crises. Lack of legitimate information about adolescence, the crises it incorporates, and its consequences to both mothers and adolescents can tremendously influence both when this phase of life approaches, it is confusing for both to respond appropriately to the situation and consequently most times it is mismanaged and Adolescents easy exposure to drugs and becoming an addict is one of its consequences adding to numerous others. The study attempted to understand the various types of encounters of mothers' upbringing adolescents dealing with numerous progression and development, to apprehend how large of a position mothers play in adolescents' lives.

Keywords:- Mother, Adolescent, Chil-Upbringing, Adolescent Crises.

I. INTRODUCTION

Every mother has their own different experiences when it comes to child upbringing just like every child is born different and there are multiple ways concerning how mothers practice nurturing. "Mothering claims a great number of years of hard work giving affection and care to a growing child and mothers as homemakers incorporate diverse exercises and capacities alongside critical venture, it is a general knowledge that housewives mothers should raise, and take care of children which include teaching, cooking, clean, wash, nurture, design, oversee accounts, direct workers, coordinate gatherings, give companionship to a spouse, mingle, and do numerous different things to easily run the house furthermore, give a solid and blissful environment to other members of the family" (Rahman 2005).

Mothering is characterized as the most 'fulfilling and powerful work' any woman will at any point have. As mothers, they sustain and profoundly mold the existences of children and families. Fathers assume a significant part, yet as mothers, they are the CEOs of the families, and very much like in the corporate world, they set the tone and how they feel influences how the entire family feels (Greenberg & Avigdor, 2009). Mothers are discovered to be the more involved in child upbringing and managing adolescents dealing with different changes and challenges, the study found the significance of the mother's role in child upbringing and how their future in huge part relies on mothers who will guide their every step from teaching, behavior modification, and

supporting and up to the extent of making many important life choices.

II. CASE STUDIES

➤ Case Study-1

A 43-year mother with three children, 8, 11, and 15 years respectively, a full-time mother taking care of her children which was never an issue for her though she had an excessive number of responsibilities as a mother, her children were obedient and manageable yet as her oldest slowly transforms into an adolescent, things are gradually switching up around the house, getting difficult to manage consistently, she noticed the transformation how her adolescent son is presently not that talkative cheerful human as he was in his school age, turning out to be exceptionally withdrawn and preferring very often to be left alone, he is easily angered upon lecturing him that he would leave home and sleep over at his friends, here the Mother is finding it extremely challenging to understand her adolescent, with all that the real problem started when he began demanding money and upon the refusal, he would break things such as; Mirrors, furniture, flower pots, and mobile phones so to avoid this she is constrained to give him money each time which is getting out of control, he even threatens her mother not to inform his father and this has been going on for quite some time now, and since her husband is barely home who is a cab driver, all the problems have to be overlooked by her, being a cab driver who makes just enough to manage home, most days they battle monetarily and with this issue, it is getting a lot harder for her to handle her adolescent at home, yet she is presently planning to send him to the boarding, for which she is saving money to send him right when she can save enough. She believes this is the only way he can be controlled and monitored as she is vulnerable and clueless to handle him at home.

➤ Case Study- 2

A 40 -year-old mother with two children, 9 years, and 14 years respectively, she is a businesswoman who owns a thrift shop which gives her less time to be with her children, initially, it was manageable as her mother, the grandparent of the children would take care of them while she is away but since they all growing up, she is attempting to manage the home without the assistance of her mother. During the pandemic of Covid19, she was compelled to buy her adolescent a mobile phone for online classes which changed everything, her 14-year-old daughter is now extremely addicted to her mobile phone that she failed in 8th standard

and now repeating the classes. Her adolescent would consistently have arguments with her when she is told not to excessively utilize her phone, she would skip a meal or family time to play games, she sleeps late at night and wakes up very late missing her classes habitually, additionally, she was caught twice sneaking out at night upon which her mobile phone was seized which made no difference as she created a lot of trouble protesting by staying in her room the whole day without going to class and threatening her mother to harm herself which continued for days and mother feeling defenseless she handed back her phone and she currently remains the same glued to her mobile phone leaving mother so distressed.

➤ *Case Study-3*

A 39-year-old mother to three children, 5, 8, and 13 respectively, she is a full-time mother her husband is a daily wage earner but heavily addicted to alcohol so the little money he earns each day is mostly spent on drinking bringing very little at home. Her 13-year-old son gradually changed, he was an easy child, to begin with, he caused no trouble as a kid but slowly he began spending more time with peers who are older than him and gradually he started going out regularly skipping classes and getting into trouble, sometimes he would come home with bruises and sometime he would just not come home, however, the genuine issue established as he started coming home intoxicated incorporating lying, cursing and stealing money at home, mother found herself in a very helpless state as her husband himself is a drunkard so they cannot simply question their son to refrain from these activities, and neighbors started complaining about things been stolen frequently and once he was caught in the act and was badly beaten by the neighbors which was terrifying and heartbreaking for her to watch and he was completely wasted and taken to hospital having no option left he is now sent to a rehab centre in a different district to seek help.

➤ *Case Study-4*

A 40-year-old mother to a 15-year-old daughter, she is a farmer working every day on her farm, having an only child she and her husband endeavored to provide everything and anything she wanted and needed even when they are struggling, as her daughter turned adolescent she was excessively spoiled to the point of forcing her parents to buy all the expensive gadgets and clothes and upon refusal, her daughter would become extremely furious and aggressively damage her belongings. Mother finds it undeniably challenging to communicate with her daughter as she is easily irritated and does not have any desire to spend time with her parents, she is jolly and happiest with her peers but at home her daughter is a different person, she is always on her phone either talking or chatting which has slowly reached a disturbing level of an excessive phone call however she was respected as an adult to intervene her privacy yet one-day to her mother's surprise a stranger lady called her mother telling her daughter is in hospital for abortion who was impregnated by her son, She was terrified and as she rushed to hospital she found her daughter in hospital crying her eyes out preparing for abortion, mother all terrified and speechless had a very hard time to deal with this situation yet helplessly

she finally decided to agree for abortion as they have no knowledge about early pregnancy, abortion and its consequences, in addition her daughter was exceptionally very young to be a mother. After the abortion, her daughter dropped out of school and presently taking a year break for recovery.

➤ *Case Study-5*

A 49-year-old mother of three children, 11, and 14. And 16 years respectively, being a full-time mother, raising three children was never easy for her, gradually turning out to be more challenging and most exceedingly terrible to be a mother to two adolescents and one nearly an adolescent. Her 16-year-old son slowly started investing more time outside and was seldom home, and even when he was home he seemed like a different person, he would lock his room and would not answer even when he is called multiple times, he would spend hours in the washroom and after he utilizes the washroom there would be strange smell which was confusing yet she respected his privacy moreover because he was becoming aggressive when she questioned anything yet Her nightmare began when her adolescent son was caught by police when he was buying illegal drugs and she got a phone call from the police station, she could hardly believe her son was into drugs but to her surprise, he was more than that, he was already an addict who was found to be involved in many illegal activities, unforeseen he is presently sent to a juvenile observation home where he will be monitored for some months and ever since the mother has been finding very difficult to eat and sleep.

III. METHODOLOGY

For the study, the research methodology used for analysis is the collection of primary data; i.e conducting case studies to gain an in-depth understanding of the journey of motherhood particularly mothering an adolescent and managing the crises adolescents go through.

IV. FINDINGS

- The struggles and negative impact of working mothers who are forced to neglect their children were identified as how it becomes difficult to interface with children at another level,
- The danger of excessive use of mobile phones and how it is deeply affecting adolescents was identified which needs serious consideration as it is impacting negatively in multiple ways which are a serious threat for the future.
- It is found that giving all autonomy to adolescents has a very negative impact as they explore new things, in the adult world which they do not understand could endanger them when they are not monitored, educated, and put forth certain boundaries.
- Parental influence has a huge effect on children, particularly adolescents who are identified, and how they become more vulnerable to addictions as they grow up watching their parents indulge in utilizing alcohol and drugs.

- It is apparent that mothers are less aware of ways to deal with or understand the adolescent crisis and how it has been impacting families negatively in numerous ways, in addition, it shows the limited source of help accessible in the study area.

V. CONCLUSION

Motherhood or mothering can be viewed as one of the hardest positions to be in as it incorporates the childhood of a kid and on the off chance it is done well, it tends to be extremely fulfilling notwithstanding, on the off chance that it is done else, it can damage the existence of a child for eternity. Here the researcher concludes the study by covering multiple explanations of the journey of motherhood, which is uniquely experienced particularly dealing with adolescent crises and how it can impact both mother and adolescent. The importance of educating both mothers and adolescents in properly managing this difficult stage is found to be a necessity and prevention intervention that can emerge out of multiple sources; Educators, Churches, and NGOs are also found to be significant in managing adolescent crises alongside mothers who are found to be helpless in many circumstances.

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